

Evaluation of the effectiveness and durability of commercial non-stick coatings

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ABSTRACT

In this study, four commercial non-stick coatings (two fluoropolymer and two ceramic) were characterized by micrography, Raman spectroscopy and energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX). A pancake batter was then baked on coated aluminum substrates. In a first test, 90 consecutive baking cycles were performed on each coated specimen. In a second test, the coatings were abraded by sanding, followed by 30 baking cycles. In both cases, take-off pressure was evaluated to extract the pancake model, as well as water sliding angle, surface roughness and surface damage. The results have shown that perfluoroalkoxyalkane (PFA) and polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) were the most effective in terms of pull-off pressure (<3 kPa) versus ceramic siloxane coatings with values between 15 and 34 kPa after 90 firings. In the different experimental stages, a positive correlation between wettability and detachment force was observed, especially for fluoropolymer coatings. However, surface roughness did not strongly correlate with the pull-off force, low values did not correlate with low values of pull-off force and vice versa. This paper proposes an objective and simple coating evaluation procedure for industrial environments. Although ceramic sol-gel coatings show potential, there is a need to improve their non-stick capability to bring them on par with traditional solutions.

1. Introduction

Anti-adherent coatings have become indispensable in the food industry because they provide functional and hydrophobic thin films on metallic substrates that enhance their demoulding, non-stick, sliding, and food removal properties. These coatings offer numerous advantages such as improved utensil cleanliness, enhanced food quality, time and energy savings in food processing, and reduced use of release agents, leading to overall production improvement and cost savings (Guerrero, 2013; Thomas, 1998).

Aluminium has emerged as a widely used substrate for anti-adherent coatings owing to its desirable characteristics, including easy processability, resistance to oxidation, light weight, good thermal conductivity, and ease of preparation for coating applications (Ashkenazi, 2019). Consequently, manufacturers frequently utilise aluminium in various food utensils, such as pans, pots, plates, trays, moulds, and sandwich makers.

Fluoropolymeric anti-adherent coatings have dominated this field since the 1960s, exhibiting outstanding qualities such as chemical inertness, self-lubrication, thermal and electrical insulation,

hydrophobicity, oleophobicity, non-stick capacity, and low surface energy (Ameduri, 2018; Gardiner, 2015). However, some studies have raised doubts regarding their suitability for specific human exposure conditions (Sajid and Ilyas, 2017). Additionally, their porous nature, especially that of polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE), and their relatively low hardness limit their application in cooking utensils subjected to high temperatures or erosive products (Biswas and Vijayan, 1992). Moreover, recycling difficulties and environmental issues associated with waste further limit their long-term use (Schmidt-Rodenkirchen et al., 2023; Wani et al., 2021).

Over the last fifteen years, alternative anti-adherent coatings such as “ceramic” or “green” coatings, produced using sol-gel techniques, have emerged. Sol-gel coatings are based on organically modified silica and offer excellent hardness, high temperature resistance, wear resistance, good adhesion to metals, and impressive hydrophobic and anti-adherence properties (Ak and Çiçek, 2021; Kumi et al., 2013). Promising advances have also been made in the development of self-healing solutions (Kumar and Subasri, 2012). However, certain drawbacks such as reduced demoulding capacity, early loss of non-stick properties, colour changes, permanent stains, and cleaning difficulties have been

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reported (Broz et al., 2015; Rossi et al., 2014).

This study focused on the evaluation and comparison of different anti-adherent coatings specifically, fluoropolymer coatings and sol-gel ceramic coatings. Thus, perfluoroalkoxy alkane (PFA) and polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) as fluoropolymeric coatings, were compared with matrix and nano sol-gel ceramic coatings. The evaluation was conducted using a pancake batter model. The assessment was performed quantitatively, considering factors such as the force/pressure required to detach the pancake batter, sliding angle of water droplets on the surfaces, surface roughness, and wear of the surfaces. The analysis included two tests: Test 1 evaluated the surfaces during and after frying 90 pancakes, and, In Test 2, the unused coated surfaces were initially subjected to artificial wear using sandpaper, followed by frying of 30 pancake batter.

The proper selection of anti-adherent coatings presents a challenge for both food utensil manufacturers and end consumers. This study aimed to provide valuable insights for making informed decisions regarding the advantages and limitations of different anti-adherent alternatives in the food industry. While some coatings have traditionally been tested qualitatively on food (Damdhar et al., 2015; NMX, 2005; NTC, 1996; Schmidt, Alex & Haering, 2002), this study adopted a quantitative approach (Ashokkumar and Adler-Nissen, 2011) (Rossi et al., 2014) to offer a more detailed and precise comparison between non-stick agents. Various factors such as the extraction force, adhesion, surface energy, and their impact on processed food were evaluated to comprehensively understand the coating performance. Among the investigated coatings, the “Matrix” sol-gel type coating by PPG Industrial Coating (USA), the siloxane type with nanoparticles “Nano” coating by Technology Umbrella (Spain) for baking applications, and the fluoropolymeric PTFE and PFA coatings by Whitford S.R.L (Brescia, Italy), were chosen for this study and all of them were applied by a specialized industry.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Specimen preparation

The substrate on which the coatings were applied was an aluminium alloy EN-AW 5083 H111. The dimensions of the specimens were $75 \times 75 \times 5$ mm. Table 1 lists the number of iterations used for the characterisation and tests.

The results obtained after measuring the different output variables were expressed as the mean value of the five iterations used for each test and coating. The dispersion was evaluated using the standard deviation of five values obtained.

The Chauvenet criterion was used as the rejection criterion. The process is based on the normal distribution and is used to determine whether a value in the data set is unusual enough to be considered an outlier (Fatchur Rochim, 2016). This criterion has been used in collecting data on roughness, sliding angle and take-off force/pressure.

2.2. Coatings

The following non-stick coatings were used: (i) Tecnimacor TF 77530, PFA-based fluoropolymer supplied by Whitford S.R.L (Brescia, Italy) and applied following supplier procedure; (ii) Tecnimacor TFI 2531 N (PTFE), PTFE-based fluoropolymer (Whitford S.R.L); (iii)

Table 1
Number of repetitions of tests on $75 \times 75 \times 5$ mm test specimens.

	AW 5083	AW 5083 +			
		PTFE	PFA	Matrix	Nano
Characterization	1	1	1	1	1
Test 1 (90 cycles)		5	5	5	5
Test 2 (sandpaper+30 cycles)		5	5	5	5

Tecnimacor 80S-088/V4146, sol-gel type (Matrix), applied according to the procedure proposed by PPG Industrial Coatings; and (iv) Tecnimacor Nano, siloxane type with nanoparticles (Nano), applied according to the procedure proposed by Umbrella Technologies. All coatings were applied by a specialist company, Tecnimacor (Córdoba, Spain).

The thicknesses of the coatings were determined using a Karl Deutsch model Leptoskop 2042 (Karl Deutsch, Wuppertal, Germany). Five measurements were taken at different points on the analysed surface.

Four aluminum samples of $10 \times 10 \times 5$ mm were prepared, on which commercial non-stick coatings were applied. The purpose was to take micrographs of these samples to examine the coating layers in detail. Thus, the samples were encapsulated in polyester resin and subsequently polished with colloidal silica. These micrographs are presented in Fig. 1. The images show notable differences in the coating structures. Fig. 1a shows a coating consisting of two layers: a very thick primer layer and a PTFE topcoat, both with a total thickness of $70\text{--}75 \mu\text{m}$. Both layers have been obtained by liquid projection with a high volume, low pressure (HVLP) spray gun. Fig. 1b again shows a coating of $150\text{--}160 \mu\text{m}$, in two layers. The first layer is a primer sprayed with an HVLP gun on the substrate and the second is a layer of PFA powder applied with an electrostatic gun. Then, the specimen was thermally cured. On the other hand, the sol-gel ceramic coating was also applied by HVLP gun, but in a wet-on-wet system reaching a thickness of $35\text{--}45 \mu\text{m}$ after curing, as shown in Fig. 1c. Finally, the siloxane-based sol-gel coating with nanoparticles was also applied by fine spraying, but in a single layer of $6\text{--}7 \mu\text{m}$ thickness (Fig. 1d).

The micrographs shown in Fig. 1 were obtained with the Leica DM6000 M optical microscope specific for materials characterization (Leica Microsistemas S.L.U, Barcelona, Spain) with Z axis, optical turret and motorized XY stage.

Bare aluminum substrates are not evaluated in this work since their use is very limited in cooking food due to their poor non-stickiness and, above all, the severe limitations established by food contact regulations (Sander et al., 2018).

2.3. Raman spectroscopy

Raman spectroscopy was used to characterise the coatings. A Raman Vis-Nir spectrophotometer equipped with a microscope (model NRS 5500, JASCO Corporation, Tokyo, Japan) was used. The spectra were used to characterise the composition of each analysed coating.

Fig. 2 shows the spectrum of the Matrix ceramic coating, known as a sol-gel type ceramic coating. This type of ceramic coating is composed of organically modified silica in the form of siloxanes or silsesquioxanes, or both. In this study, a peak near 500 cm^{-1} (485 cm^{-1}) was observed, which is characteristic of siloxanes with a cyclic structure with a D₁-type ring. The peak close to 800 cm^{-1} (790 cm^{-1}) is compatible with silicates. The peak close to 980 cm^{-1} (1000 cm^{-1}) indicates Si–O–Si and its ladder structure type Q².

The spectrum of the PTFE-based coating, which is composed of a fluoropolymer along with other pigments and fillers, is shown in Fig. 3. The spectrum of this type of coating showed characteristic peaks compatible with those of PTFE. The peaks close to 291 cm^{-1} (287 cm^{-1}), 384 cm^{-1} , 1299 cm^{-1} and 1380 cm^{-1} are characteristic of junction C–F, F₂, and various modes of symmetry (Legéay et al., 1998).

The spectrum of the PFA coating is shown in Fig. 4. Fluoropolymeric coatings of this type exhibit a practically identical Raman spectrum response to that of PTFE. The literature indicates that the characteristic peaks are the same in these two fluoropolymers (Legéay et al., 1998), and the results have verified this fact.

The Raman spectrum of the Nano coating, based on siloxane and nanoparticles applied by sol-gel, is shown in Fig. 5. This analysis did not allow sufficient information related to its constitution to be obtained.

Fig. 1. Fluoropolymeric and ceramic coatings: a) PTFE, b) PFA, c) Matrix, d) Nano.

Fig. 2. Raman spectrum of Matrix ceramic coating.

2.4. EDX spectroscopy

The Nano sol-gel-type coating was analysed by energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX) using a JEOL JSM 7800F field emission scanning electron microscope (JEOL Ltd. Tokyo, Japan). Table 2 presents the EDX results.

After analysis of the results, it was possible to determine that the composition is compatible with a matrix with high concentrations of aluminium (Al) and silica (Si) as the main components.

2.5. Experimental plan

An experimental plan was designed to evaluate the effects of various non-stick coatings after their repeated use in pancake production. First, an experiment of 90 consecutive frying cycles was designed; on the other hand, the coatings were subjected to artificial wear by sanding, and then 30 pancake frying cycles were conducted. The results obtained after

measuring the different output variables were expressed as the mean value of the five iterations used for each test and coating. The distribution was evaluated using the standard deviation of five values obtained.

The accompanying diagram outlines the experimental plan (Fig. 6).

2.6. Pancake batter elaboration and cooking

The dough was comprised of 50 g pasteurised egg white, 30 g sunflower oil, 150 g milk, 125 g rice flour, and 20 g white sugar. The mixture was prepared in a metal bowl using a whisk and stirred. The ingredients were added in the following order: milk, egg whites, oil, flour, and sugar. The mixture was stirred continuously until a homogeneous mass was obtained without lumps or fluid.

The selected dough can be easily replicated and has the advantage of being highly adhesive, mainly because of its sugar content and the type of flour used (Adhikari et al., 2001). For this reason, the adhesion

Fig. 3. Raman spectrum of PTFE coating.

Fig. 4. Raman spectrum of PFA coating.

Fig. 5. Raman spectrum of Nano coating.

Table 2
Percentage of the main components in the Nano sol-gel coating.

Element	O	Al	Si	Cl
Weight (%)	43.59 ± 0.24	20.76 ± 0.11	35.31 ± 0.16	0.25 ± 0.09

phenomena on the surfaces appear relatively quickly. In the first test, 90 consecutive cooking cycles were performed. In the second test, artificial wear was induced on the specimen surface and 30 consecutive cooking cycles were subsequently performed.

For sample cooking, a circular electric griddle with Ø250 mm and 3 kW power (METRO Markets GmbH, Düsseldorf, Germany) was used. The power was regulated so that the surface temperature of the coated specimens reached 210 ± 10 °C. The mixture was transferred into a 12 ml disposable syringe, and a volume of 2 ml was deposited in the centre of the square specimen without applying any oil or grease. The pancake samples were cooked for 5 min. The pancake was approximately circular, with an average diameter of 27,6 mm and a thickness of 2–3 mm.

Fig. 6. Graphical scheme of the experimental plan.

2.7. Evaluation of the surface properties

The slip angle (SA) is the angle that a flat surface forms with respect to the horizontal at the instant that a deposited drop of water slides. It is an indicator of the wettability of the surface. Thus, the sliding angle in contact with water was measured using a turntable equipped with a digital goniometer with a 0.05° appreciation. The turntable rotates at a speed of $1^\circ/\text{s}$. The deposited drops are $50 \mu\text{l}$ of purified and deionised water. The measurement was repeated five times, with care taken to distribute it over the studied surface.

A Mitutoyo SJ-201 profilometer (Mitutoyo Corporation, Kakatsu-ku, Kawasaki, Kanagawa, Japan) was used to obtain the linear roughness, Ra and Rz, of the specimen surfaces. These parameters are used in surface metrology to quantify the surface roughness and defined in the UNE-EN ISO 21920-2:2023 standard. The arithmetic mean roughness (Ra) represents the average height of the peaks and valleys with respect to a central line in a specific evaluation length. The total height mean roughness (Rz) provides information on the total amplitude of the irregularities on the surface, i.e., the difference between the highest deviations (peaks) and the lowest deviations (valleys). Values were obtained after repeating the measurements five times.

Surface photographs were taken using a digital microscope (Leica DVM6, Wetzlar, Germany) and MountainsMap surface analysis software (Digital Surf, Besançon, France).

2.8. Induced wear

Surface wear was produced using SiC sandpaper (Struers-Roper Technologies, Inc., Sarasota, Florida, USA) with a FEPA P1200 grit size. In this procedure, a force of 20 N was applied to the substrate using a 20 N weight placed on the specimen with the coated side down and against the surface of the abrasive paper. The specimen was moved carefully at a speed of 150 mm/s on a paper fixed to the worktable. Wear was applied in two perpendicular directions and the cycle was repeated 15 times in each direction.

2.9. “Take-off” detaching force

To determine the take-off force, an Imada DS2-50N dynamometer (Imada Inc., Northbrook, USA) was used. The device has a threaded rod at its end. A prismatic part with dimensions of $50 \times 50 \times 25 \text{ mm}$ was manufactured by milling from a piece of extruded PTFE bar. On one of the faces of the prism at a height of 5 mm, a threaded hole was made to screw the dynamometer rod. The pancake demoulding process occurred immediately after frying. To achieve this, the nonthreaded face of the rectangular PTFE prism was placed in contact with the mass of the fried pancake. Subsequently, the dynamometer, together with the threaded

rod and rectangular PTFE prism, was horizontally displaced at a constant speed of 10 mm/s until the fried mass was completely detached from the specimen. In each experiment, the maximum force required for detachment was recorded.

2.10. Statistical analysis

The results have been statistically analysed to understand the relationships in the evolution of surface roughness, wettability and detachment strength between the types of coating under study, before and after the cooking process. Furthermore, an analysis of variance (ANOVA) has been performed on the proposed linear regression model to determine the take-off force (output) as a function of the type of coating (categorical input) and the number of cooking cycles (numerical input), determining the influence of each factor on this response. This study was carried out using Minitab v.19 statistical software (Minitab, LLC., State College, PA, USA).

3. Results and discussion

The results are presented in the natural order in which the work was performed: initial characterisation of the coatings, followed by the results of the frying and detachment experiments. Additionally, the results and discussion are presented in the following order: initially, the detachment force was measured, followed by the roughness, sliding angle, and finally, the surface damage.

3.1. Coated state of the specimens

The surface and wettability properties of the bare substrate and the applied non-stick coatings were characterised. Table 3 presents a

Table 3

Thickness, roughness (Ra and Rz) and sliding angle (SA) measured with a $50 \mu\text{l}$ water drop on the bare substrate and coated with different coatings before use.

Material	Thickness, t (μm)	Ra (μm)	Rz (μm)	Sliding angle, SA ($^\circ$)
Aluminum alloy substrate (supply state)	-	0.33 ± 0.07	1.93 ± 0.40	55.9 ± 2.6
PFA	157.5 ± 0.5	0.74 ± 0.10	4.71 ± 0.27	18.5 ± 1.3
PTFE	71.5 ± 0.4	2.73 ± 0.02	22.74 ± 4.58	25.5 ± 1.1
Matrix	49.0 ± 0.2	0.80 ± 0.07	5.53 ± 0.79	32.2 ± 1.3
Nano	6.9 ± 0.3	0.49 ± 0.08	2.60 ± 0.34	22.3 ± 0.8

summary of the results of the study.

The thickest coating was that of the PFA, at 157.5 μm , followed by PTFE, Matrix, and Nano (71.5, 49.0, and 6.9 μm , respectively). The differences are substantial because the PFA-type coating is two and >20 times thicker than the PTFE and Nano coatings, respectively. Further, the Nano sol-gel coating was noticeably thinner than the other coatings.

Regarding roughness, the roughest surface is that of PTFE ($R_a = 2.73$ μm and $R_z = 22.74$ μm). PFA and Matrix coatings exhibited similar roughness values, but approximately four times less than that of PTFE ($R_a = 0.74$ and 0.84 μm , respectively), and the Nano sol-gel coating exhibited the lowest roughness, similar to that of the uncoated substrate ($R_a = 0.49$ μm).

Characterisation of the sliding angle showed that the coatings had lower water wettability, and it was observed that PFA had the best performance (with values of 18.5°), followed by the Nano (22.3°), PTFE (25.5°), and Matrix (32.2°) coatings.

The values obtained for the roughness of the PTFE and PFA coatings were consistent with those of other studies (Akinci and Cobanoglu, 2009) and the same is true for the sliding angle (SA) (Kiuru and Alakoski, 2004).

3.2. Maximum take-off (detachment) force

The maximum take-off force required to detach the cooked pancake batter from the four types of coatings used was determined. In Test 1, the maximum detachment forces at 30, 60, and 90 consecutive cycles of cooked pancakes on the coated substrates were measured. In Test 2, another set of coated specimens were prepared and abraded with sandpaper, and the detachment force was measured after 30 cycles of cooking. The results are shown in Fig. 7.

The results showed substantial differences between the fluoropolymeric coatings and sol-gel types. In all cases, the PTFE and PFA coatings exhibited detachment forces lower than 2 N. The sol-gel coatings, especially above 30 cooking cycles, exhibited detachment forces between 5 and 10 times higher than those of the fluoropolymers.

In the case of the test with the artificially eroded initial coatings (Test 2), the differences were still very noticeable, and the detachment forces were 7–14 times lower for the fluoropolymeric coatings.

In short, considering the take-off force as an indicator of the non-adherence capacity of coatings to food dough, sol-gel coatings showed worse results, with higher force values than those measured for fluoropolymeric coatings. This effect was consistent in the two states of the study, on both the intact and previously worn surfaces of the coatings. In addition, these differences became more pronounced as the number of cooking cycles increased.

Among the fluorine-based coatings, PTFE shows a slight worsening of its non-stick capacity owing to a persistent increase of take-off force (0.68, 1.47, and 1.93 N after 30, 60, and 90 consecutive cooking cycles, respectively). This behaviour suggests that the non-stick capabilities suffer slight degradation, although the take-off forces are still low.

This degradation effect did not appear in the PFA coating, which exhibited a take-off force below 1.5 N in all cases. In fact, the take-off force seems to decrease with use. It has been postulated that this could be due to the combination of a favourable change in the topography of the surface, a lubrication effect due to the sunflower oil used in the dough, and the relatively greater hardness of the PFA fluoropolymer compared to PTFE (Guerrero-Vaca and Rodríguez-Alabanda, 2022). Nevertheless, it is relevant to note that the measured detachment forces were particularly low, and even lower than those registered for PTFE after 30 cooking cycles.

Regarding sol-gel coatings, those of the Matrix type showed a somewhat better behaviour than the Nano type because the detachment force measured seemed to stabilise at approximately 10 N after 30 cooking cycles. In contrast, the Nano coating reached values of more than 20 N after 90 cooking cycles and was by far the worst in terms of the detachment force.

These results are consistent with those of previous studies that were consulted, which showed that the maximum detaching force on PTFE was 4–10 times lower than that obtained for ceramic coatings, such as TiAlN, ZrN, or ZrO₂ (Ashokkumar and Adler-Nissen, 2011), considering that the referenced study did not compare detachment forces after continued use of the material.

From the detachment forces measured in this experiment, it was possible to model the pressure (force per unit area) corresponding to the surface tension that appeared when trying to remove food dough from the surface. Stresses on the surface of the dough are transverse, since they are parallel to the surface (shear or shear stress, τ) and are caused by a shear stress (detaching force). Assuming the average contact surface area of the pancakes of 27.6 mm diameter, the maximum take-off pressures are listed in Table 4.

Finally, for both states (Test 1 and Test 2), the fluoropolymer coatings were more efficient than the tested sol-gel coatings. In both cases, the detaching forces and consequently the detachment pressures at the end of the Test 1 were between 10 and 18 times lower than those measured on the ceramics, specifically 0.80 and 3.20 kPa for fluoropolymers and 15.1 and 34.5 kPa for sol-gel ceramics. In short, it has been observed that the behaviour of the coatings both without and with induced wear follow the same pattern, that is, the fluoropolymers of both PFA and PTFE have better behaviour than the Matrix type ceramic and the nano-type ceramic.

Fig. 7. Value of the maximum detachment forces of the pancake dough: a) test 1, after 30, 60, and 90 cooking cycles; b) test 2, after artificial wear +30 cooking cycles.

Table 4

Values of Ra, Rz, SA and the maximum take-off pressure after 90 cooking cycles of pancake units on the different coated surfaces.

Material	Nr. cooking cycles	Ra (μm)	Rz (μm)	SA ($^\circ$)	Max. take-off pressure after cooking cycles (kPa)
Aluminum alloy substrate (supply state)	1	0.33	1.93 \pm 0.40	–	51.30 \pm 9.16
PFA	90	1.15 \pm 0.65	16.92 \pm 0.98	9.8 \pm 0.5	0.83 \pm 1.11
PTFE	90	4.40 \pm 1.20	36.53 \pm 6.57	26.9 \pm 0.9	3.22 \pm 1.05
Matrix	90	0.92 \pm 0.25	16.60 \pm 1.12	53.4 \pm 1.1	15.09 \pm 5.58
Nano	90	0.55 \pm 0.31	12.27 \pm 0.79	33.0 \pm 8.4	34.49 \pm 12.15

3.3. Sliding angle measurements

The observed changes in the sliding angle (SA) as a consequence of wear indicates that wettability is sensitive to the wear of the surfaces. This can be seen in Table 5, where the sliding angle (SA) measured for 50 μl water drops on each non-stick surface was recorded before cooking, after each set of cycles of Test 1, after abrasive wear by sandpaper, and after Test 2.

The SA values of the PFA coating decreased from 18.5 $^\circ$ in the initial state to 9.8 $^\circ$ after 90 frying cycles. Thus, the sliding angle decreased significantly and as seen, the take-off force increased initially and then stabilized between 0.5 and 1.5 N. Similar trends were observed for the sliding angle and take-off force, although at different intensities. In sum, when the sliding angle decreased, the detaching force decreased when the PFA coating was used.

PFA coating is a film, i.e., a polymer sheet, and small particles are likely embedded in its structure, or small deformations are created that modify the topography with some proximity to a hierarchical surface, such as a Cassie-Baxter regime (Wang et al., 2011). The lubricating effect of the sunflower oil used, as mentioned above, may also have contributed to the changes in sliding angle. In short, it is likely that the combination of the effects described caused the sliding angle to decrease for at least 90 cooking cycles.

For the PTFE coatings, a similar trend was observed; however, it was somewhat weaker. Thus, the SA values remained relatively unchanged (25–27 $^\circ$), and there was an increase in the maximum detachment force between cooking cycles 30, 60, and 90 (0.68, 1.47, and 1.93 N, respectively). In summary, when the sliding angle increased slightly, the take-off force increased.

For the sol-gel ceramic coatings, a decrease in the sliding angle was

Table 5

Sliding angle measurements SA ($^\circ$) for a 50 μl water drop.

Material	Nr of cooking cycles				After abrasion	Abrasion +30 cooking cycles
	0	30	60	90		
Substrate	55.9 \pm 2.6	–	–	–	–	–
PFA	18.5 \pm 1.3	10.5 \pm 0.5	11.5 \pm 0.9	9.8 \pm 0.5	29.5 \pm 4.2	25.2 \pm 7.8
PTFE	25.5 \pm 1.1	25.6 \pm 2.5	26.2 \pm 1.3	26.9 \pm 0.9	39.2 \pm 6.8	20.6 \pm 3.3
Matrix	32.2 \pm 1.3	26.7 \pm 1.7	27.2 \pm 2.3	53.4 \pm 1.1	48.0 \pm 5.9	20.7 \pm 4.0
Nano	22.3 \pm 0.8	19.6 \pm 2.0	30.1 \pm 7.0	33.0 \pm 8.4	48.9 \pm 8.9	31.1 \pm 2.4

observed with an increase in the number of cooking cycles. These values were much higher than those obtained using fluoropolymers. Thus, after 90 cooking cycles, the values were very high (56.4 $^\circ$ for Matrix and 33 $^\circ$ for Nano), and the coatings were very wettable when in contact with water. In addition, the behaviour was contrary to that observed in fluoropolymeric coatings, and the highest detachment forces were measured on the Nano coating (20.6 N), although this coating presented SA values somewhat lower than those of the Matrix coating. In any case, the SA values of both sol-gel ceramic coatings were very high, and it was not reasonable to establish an agreement between the sliding angle, detachment force, and their evolution.

Finally, it can be stated that the sliding angle (SA) is a good indicator of the detachability of this type of non-stick coating. Therefore, it is particularly sensitive to the non-stick responses of the fluoropolymeric (PFA and PTFE) coatings. For sol-gel coatings, an increase in the SA value may be associated with an increase in the detaching force. However, among the sol-gel coatings analysed, no consistent results were obtained.

3.4. Surface roughness modification

The surface roughness Ra was measured during different phases of the experiment, and the results are summarized in Fig. 8. Besides, Table 4 presents Ra, Rz values after 90 cooking cycles.

In the case of PFA, the Ra value increased from 0.74 to 1.15 μm after 90 cooking cycles. Further, Ra increased to 0.92 μm when the coating was worn by abrasion and decreased to 0.84 μm after the 30 additional cooking cycles were performed. These changes in roughness were insignificant and demonstrated the robustness, resistance, and durability of the PFA coatings (Guerrero-Vaca et al., 2019).

For the PTFE surface, the value of Ra increased from 2.73 to 4.40 μm after 90 cooking cycles; after abrasion, Ra decreased to 4.32 μm and finally to 3.68 μm after a further 30 cooking cycles. This was the coating with the highest roughness among the analysed samples. The relatively low hardness of PTFE and its rough topography caused this increase in roughness (Dhanumalayan and Joshi, 2018).

The sol-gel Matrix material exhibited a very slight Ra variation, with more homogeneous values from 0.80 to 0.92 μm after cooking cycles, 0.70 μm after abrasion and, finally, 0.75 μm after additional cooking. Ceramic materials are hard (Ohmura and Matsuoka, 2003), which explains why the initial roughness remained almost unchanged.

Finally, the Nano coating exhibited Ra values of 0.49–0.55 μm (before and after cooking cycles) and 0.53–1.14 μm (after abrasion and additional cooking). A notable increase in roughness was observed when the coating was subjected to induced abrasion and used 30 times to cook dough (greater than double the initial value). This indicates possible damage to the surface, with a consequent change in the surface morphology of the coating, which may influence its non-stick capabilities. However, Ra values remained relatively low.

It is possible to postulate that the non-stick response, that is, the force or detachment pressure, does not show a direct relationship with the surface roughness, at least in the tested materials. Thus, it was verified that in the case of the sol-gel ceramic coatings studied, low Ra values produced high debonding force values, whereas for PFA, low values produced low debonding forces. However, PTFE is contradictory because relatively high Ra values produce lower detachment stresses than those of the proposed sol-gel materials. Adhesion phenomena are more related to surface energy (Baldan, 2012), that is, they depend mainly on the chemical interaction between the food dough and the coating and less on the roughness of the latter when this parameter is at reasonable levels.

3.5. Surface affectation

The photographs shown in Fig. 9 were taken using a confocal microscope during different phases of the experiment. The state objects of

Fig. 8. Mean roughness (Ra) values in the initial coated state (without damage), after 90 cooking cycles, after abrasion, and after abrasion + 30 cooking cycles in the coatings.

Fig. 9. High resolution 2D images of the surface of the coatings used: a) PFA, b) PTFE, c) Matrix, and d) Nano; and from left to right: initial condition, after 90 cooking cycles, and after abrasive wear and 30 cooking cycles.

the study were before cooking, after 90 cooking cycles, and after abrasive wear and 30 cooking cycles.

The Matrix coating surface appeared to be worn after 90 cooking cycles, as indicated by visible copper-coloured stains. When subjected to abrasive wear, it does not exhibit visible damage despite the registered loss of efficiency.

The Nano coating was clearly worn after 90 cooking cycles, and after wear and 30 cooking cycles, it exhibited superficial damage.

Both the PFA and PTFE coatings showed no apparent or significant damage in the analysed states.

In short, the damage observed is severe in the case of sol-gel ceramic coatings, very severe for the Nano type and less severe for the Matrix type, which is in agreement with other studies (Rossi et al., 2014). However, for the coatings of fluoropolymeric origin, no relevant effects were observed. The surface appearance observed in these micrographs is a faithful reflection of the non-stick behaviour of the coatings and is related to the detachment force values obtained.

3.6. Statistical analysis

The bar charts in Fig. 10 shows the statistical comparison about the evolution of Ra and SA values from the initial state and after 90 cooking cycles across the coating type.

It can be seen that, in the initial state, the PTFE coating shows the higher Ra = 4.40 μm , while the other coatings (PFA and ceramics) have lower values up to less than 25% compared to the higher value. The Rz values, in Table 4, are strongly correlated with those obtained for Ra, as can be verified through the Pearson correlation coefficients shown in Table 6.

Regarding the initial sliding angle (SA) measured before using the coated specimens, the bar chart in Fig. 10 shows that Matrix ceramic coating shows the higher SA value while the PFA coating presents the lower value of SA of less than a half with respect the higher. Thus, in the initial state (Tables 3 and 6), it can be concluded that the surface roughness defined by Ra, Rz values does not present a strong correlation with the measured SA values, which is an indication that wettability depends largely on the type of coating based on its surface energy.

In the same way, the bar graph in Fig. 10 shows the comparison between the coatings on the measured values for Ra and SA after 90 cooking cycles. In this case, it has been observed how the increase in the SA value has been very significant in the case of ceramic coatings

Fig. 10. Comparison of Ra (a) and SA (b) across the type of coating and evolution from the initial state (soft colour) and after 90 cooking cycles (dark colour).

Table 6

Correlation coefficients (Pearson) of Ra, Rz, SA and the detaching force, in the initial state and after 90 cooking cycles.

Nr. cooking cycles	Factors	Ra (μm)	Rz (μm)	SA ($^{\circ}$)	Force (N)
0	Ra (μm)	–	0.999	–0.323	–
	Rz (μm)	0.999	–	–0.287	–
	SA ($^{\circ}$)	–0.323	–0.287	–	–
90	Ra (μm)	–	0.997	–0.199	–0.562
	Rz (μm)	0.997	–	–0.160	–0.596
	SA ($^{\circ}$)	–0.199	–0.160	–	–0.468
	Force (N)	–0.562	–0.596	–0.468	–

(Matrix and Nano), while in the case of fluoropolymeric coatings (PFA and PTFE) the SA has remained stable and has even decreased.

Furthermore, it can be stated that lower values in the SA allowed lower detaching forces, especially in fluoropolymeric coatings but also a low roughness value (Ra, Rz) does not guarantee a small detaching force. Besides, the Pearson correlation coefficients in Table 6 once again have shown that it does not exist a strong correlation between the roughness parameters (Ra, Rz) and the sliding angle after a prolonged use. However, a certain negative correlation is shown between the value of SA and that of the detachment force so that when SA increases the detachment force decreases corroborating the greater influence of the physical-chemical nature of the material used in the coating on the wettability and, consequently, on the detaching force.

On the other hand, a linear regression model has been proposed (Equation (1)) to determine the detaching force (output) as a function of coating type (categorical input) and number of cooking cycles (numerical).

$$\text{Detaching force (N)} = 1.97 + 0.099 \cdot \text{Nr. of cooking cycles} +$$

$$+ 0.0 \text{ (if Matrix coated)} + 3.99 \cdot \text{(if Nano coated)} - 7.03 \cdot \text{(if PFA coated)} - 6.55 \text{ (if PTFE coated)} \quad (1)$$

The statistic $R^2 = 72.02\%$ and the normal probability plot in Fig. 11 corroborates a good fitting of the proposed model with respect to the experimental data. Moreover, the analysis of variance (ANOVA) showed that the most influencing factor in the detaching force/detaching pressure is the coating type ($p = 0.042 < 0.05$ in Table 7), while the number of cooking cycles has a lower effect. This fact is corroborated by the Pareto chart shown in Fig. 11.

Fig. 11. a) Normal probability plot and b) Pareto chart of standardized effect, both of detaching force (N) as a function of coating type and number of cooking cycles.

Table 7

ANOVA statistics for detaching force as a function of coating type and number of cooking cycles.

Source	DF	Adj. SS	Adj. MS	F-value	P-value
Regression	4	326.19	81.55	4.50	0.041
Nr. of cooking cycles	1	70.57	70.57	3.90	0.089
Coating type	3	255.63	85.21	4.71	0.042
Error	7	126.76	18.11		
Total	11	452.95			

4. Conclusions

In this study, we successfully designed and evaluated a control food mass to compare the performance and durability of different non-stick coatings. The experimental protocol evaluated the wear of coatings by examining the release force, water sliding angle (SA), roughness, and surface micrographs. The release force/pressure proved to be a reliable indicator of the non-stick properties of the coating. The wettability was consistent for the fluoropolymer coatings but inadequate for the sol-gel ceramic non-stick coatings. Roughness (Ra) was not directly correlated with non-stick or release resistance. Fluoropolymer coatings showed the highest effectiveness as non-stick food coatings, followed by Matrix and Nano coating materials using sol-gel technology. The proposed non-stick evaluation procedure is cost-effective, easy to perform, and suitable for industrial applications. Sol-gel coatings exhibit potential for frying foods but require improvements in wear resistance and non-stick capability to match the performance of traditional fluoropolymer coatings.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

G. Guerrero-Vacas: Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision, Software, Resources, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **F. Comino:** Visualization, Formal analysis, Data curation. **O. Rodríguez-Alabanda:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Project administration, Investigation.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Guillermo Guerrero-Vacas reports financial support was provided by Spain Ministry of Science and Innovation. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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References

- Adhikari, B., Howes, T., Bhandari, B.R., Truong, V., 2001. Stickiness in foods: a review of mechanisms and test methods. *Int. J. Food Prop.* 4 (1), 1–33. <https://doi.org/10.1081/JFP-100002186>.
- Ak, A., Çiçek, B., 2021. Synthesis and characterization of hydrophobic glass-ceramic thin film derived from colloidal silica, zirconium(IV) propoxide and methyltrimethoxysilane via sol-gel method. *J. Sol. Gel Sci. Technol.* 98 (1), 252–263. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10971-021-05482-5>.
- Akinci, A., Cobanoglu, E., 2009. Coating of Al mould surfaces with polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE), fluorinated ethylene propylene (FEP), perfluoroalkoxy (PFA) and ethylene-tetrafluoroethylene (ETFE). *E-Polymers* 33, 1–7.
- Ameduri, B., 2018. Fluoropolymers: the right material for the right applications. *Chem. Eur. J.* 24 (71), 18830–18841. <https://doi.org/10.1002/chem.201802708>.
- Ashkenazi, D., 2019. How aluminum changed the world: a metallurgical revolution through technological and cultural perspectives. *Technol. Forecast. Soc. Change* 143 (November 2018), 101–113. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2019.03.011>.
- Baldan, A., 2012. Adhesion phenomena in bonded joints. *Int. J. Adhesion Adhes.* 38, 95–116. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijadhadh.2012.04.007>.
- Biswas, S.K., Vijayan, K., 1992. Friction and wear of PTFE - a review. *Wear* 158 (1–2), 193–211. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0043-1648\(92\)90039-B](https://doi.org/10.1016/0043-1648(92)90039-B).
- Broz, C.C., Taylor, D.C., Barr, J., 2015. Non-stick “green” cookware : does it measure up to manufacturers’ claims. *Journal of Tourism, Hospitality and Culinary Arts* 7 (1), 58–75.
- Damdhar, V.S., Pande, K.N., Peshwe, D.R., Gogte, C.L., 2015. To investigate the wear mechanism on cryogenic treatment of PTFE-Mica filled composite coatings in cookware. *Trans. Indian Inst. Met.* 68 (4), 611–621. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12666-014-0491-7>.
- Dhanumalayan, E., Joshi, G.M., 2018. Performance properties and applications of polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE)—a review. *Adv. Compos. Hybrid Mater.* 1 (2), 247–268. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42114-018-0023-8>.
- Fatchur Rochim, A., 2016. Chauvenet’s criterion, peirce’s criterion, and thompson’s criterion (literatures review). March, 3–5.
- Gardiner, J., 2015. Fluoropolymers: origin, production, and industrial and commercial applications. *Aust. J. Chem.* 68 (1), 13–22. <https://doi.org/10.1071/CH14165>.
- Guerrero-Vaca, G., Rodríguez-Alabanda, O., 2022. Analysis of wear phenomena produced by erosion with abrasive particles against fluoropolymeric coatings. *Polymers* 2022 14 (21), 4617. <https://doi.org/10.3390/POLYM14214617>. Page 4617, 14.
- Guerrero-Vaca, G., Rodríguez-Alabanda, Ó., Romero, P.E., Soriano, C., Molero, E., Lambarri, J., 2019. Stripping of PFA fluoropolymer coatings using a Nd:YAG laser (Q-Switch) and an Yb fiber laser (CW). *Polymers* 11 (11), 1738. <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym11111738>.

- Guerrero, G., 2013. Análisis comparativo de los procesos de eliminación de recubrimientos antiadherentes fluoropoliméricos en superficies metálicas entre tecnologías láser y pirolíticas. Universidad de Málaga, Servicio de Publicaciones.
- Kiuru, M., Alakoski, E., 2004. Low sliding angles in hydrophobic and oleophobic coatings prepared with plasma discharge method. *Mater. Lett.* 58 (16), 2213–2216. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matlet.2004.01.024>.
- Kumar, N., Subasri, R., 2012. Corrosion protection and self-healing by sol-gel process: a review of recent patent literature. *Recent Pat. Corros. Sci.* 2 (2), 148–163. <https://doi.org/10.2174/2210683911202020148>.
- Kumi, A.K., Chelashaw, A., Zhang, Y., Li, L., 2013. Design of experiment: a statistical approach to understanding factors influencing surface properties of sol-gel based non-stick ceramic coatings. *Adv. Mater. Res.* 622, 420–425. <https://doi.org/10.4028/www.scientific.net/AMR.622-623.420>.
- Legeay, G., Coudreuse, A., Legeais, J.-M., Werner, L., Bulou, A., Buzaré, J.-Y., Emery, J., Silly, G., 1998. AF fluoropolymer for optical use: spectroscopic and surface energystudies; comparison with other fluoropolymers. *Eur. Polym. J.* 34 (10), 1457–1465. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0014-3057\(97\)00289-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0014-3057(97)00289-9).
- NMX, 2005. NMX-W-152-SCFI-2005. Aluminium and its Alloys – Cookware with Antiadherent- Specifications and Test Methods. Normas Mejicanas, pp. 1–17.
- NTC, 1996. NTC 2169. Household Appliances. Aluminium Ware for Cooking, Frying and Baking (Pp. 1–25. NTC. Normas Técnicas Colombianas.
- Ohmura, T., Matsuoka, S., 2003. Evaluation of mechanical properties of ceramic coatings on a metal substrate. *Surf. Coating. Technol.* 169 (170), 728–731. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0257-8972\(03\)00210-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0257-8972(03)00210-X).
- Rossi, S., Gai, G., De Benedetto, R., 2014. Functional and perceptive aspects of non-stick coatings for cookware. *Mater. Des.* 53, 782–790. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matdes.2013.07.079>.
- Sajid, M., Ilyas, M., 2017. PTFE-coated non-stick cookware and toxicity concerns: a perspective. *Environ. Sci. Pollut. Control Ser.* 24 (30), 23436–23440. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-017-0095-y>.
- Sander, S., Kappenstein, O., Ebner, I., Fritsch, K.A., Schmidt, R., Pfaff, K., Luch, A., 2018. Release of aluminium and thallium ions from uncoated food contact materials made of aluminium alloys into food and food simulant. *PLoS One* 13 (7), 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0200778>.
- Schmidt-Rodenkirchen, A., Gerdes, T., Hintzer, K., Schlipf, M., 2023. Strategies for closing the material cycles in the recycling of fluoropolymers. *Chem. Ing. Tech.* 95 (8), 1215–1227. <https://doi.org/10.1002/cite.202300039>.
- Schmidt, Alex, Haering, C., 2002. Evaluation of commercial nonstick coatings for U.S. Army field-feeding cookware. Technical Report NATICK/TR-02/017. July 2001.
- Thomas, P., 1998. The use of fluoropolymers for non-stick cooking utensils. *JOCCA - Surface Coatings International* 81 (12), 604–609. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02693055>.
- Wani, W.A., Pathan, S., Bose, S., 2021. The journey of alternative and sustainable substitutes for “single-use” plastics. *Advanced Sustainable Systems* 5 (12), 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.1002/advsu.202100085>.